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SERIEDAD Y CALIDAD

Becoming a Spanish professor
in the North American Midwest

EFL Teachers' Perceptions on
Teaching Students Within the
Autistic Spectrum Disorder

Le français au Chili : d'un
passé glorieux à de nouvelles
opportunités dans un monde
hispanophone

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MESSAGE DE LA DIRECTRICE DU CONSEIL DE RÉDACTION

Nous sommes heureux de vous présenter un nouveau numéro de *ELT Connections*, une publication consacrée à la réflexion, à l'analyse critique et au partage d'expériences significatives dans l'enseignement des langues étrangères. Ce Volume 4, Numéro 1 paraît à un moment particulièrement important : l'inauguration récente de l'Institut des Langues Étrangères et des Cultures (ILEC) de l'Université Bernardo O'Higgins. Cette nouvelle unité académique, dédiée à l'enseignement des langues et à la promotion de la compréhension interculturelle, naît avec un fort engagement envers la communauté, en accord avec le modèle institutionnel de *Vinculación con el Medio* (« Engagement avec la société»). Cette édition s'inscrit ainsi dans un contexte institutionnel renouvelé qui renforce notre mission de diffuser le savoir au-delà de la salle de classe, en créant des espaces d'apprentissage, de dialogue culturel et de collaboration avec des publics variés.

Ce numéro réunit des contributions portant sur des thématiques actuelles, explorées depuis des perspectives géographiques et pédagogiques diverses. Nous commençons par une Lettre à la rédaction qui propose une réflexion critique sur les méthodes d'enseignement contemporaines, en interrogeant l'équilibre entre tradition et innovation dans les classes de langues d'aujourd'hui. Dans la rubrique *Dans la salle de classe*, nous explorons la valeur des pauses cérébrales comme outils pour améliorer la concentration, l'énergie et l'expérience d'apprentissage globale des étudiant.e.s.

Dans notre section *Entretien*, nous découvrons le témoignage d'une professeure américaine qui enseigne l'espagnol aux États-Unis. Elle partage les défis culturels et pédagogiques liés à l'enseignement d'une langue étrangère dans son propre pays. Par ailleurs, la section *Coin international* nous invite à élargir notre regard grâce à trois récits : une enseignante de langue maternelle anglaise évoque son expérience dans un pays d'Asie du Sud-Est, soulignant les dynamiques interculturelles qui influencent les pratiques en classe ; une analyse de l'enseignement du français au Chili examine le rôle et la position actuels de cette langue dans le paysage éducatif local ; et enfin, un professeur brésilien partage sa perspective sur l'enseignement du portugais au Chili, offrant une lecture riche sur l'expansion de cette langue et sa pertinence culturelle dans le contexte latino-américain.

Ce volume réaffirme notre engagement envers une éducation linguistique critique, ancrée dans les contextes et ouverte sur le monde. Nous espérons que les contributions de ce numéro susciteront des réflexions pédagogiques, favoriseront le dialogue interdisciplinaire et contribueront au développement continu de notre communauté d'enseignants de langues et de cultures.

Virginie Delalande

*Vice-rectrice à l'engagement communautaire
(Vinculación con el Medio)*

MESSAGE OF THE DIRECTOR OF THE EDITORIAL BOARD

We are pleased to present a new edition of ELT Connections, a publication devoted to reflection, critical analysis, and the dissemination of meaningful experiences in foreign language teaching. This Volume 4, Issue 1 is released at a particularly significant moment: the recent inauguration of the Institute of Foreign Languages and Cultures (ILEC) at Universidad Bernardo O'Higgins. This newly established academic unit, focused on language education and the promotion of intercultural understanding, emerges with a strong commitment to community engagement, in line with the university's institutional model of Outreach and Public Engagement (Vinculación con el Medio). This edition is thus framed by a renewed institutional context that strengthens our mission to extend knowledge beyond the classroom, creating spaces for learning, cultural dialogue, and collaboration with diverse audiences.

This issue brings together contributions that address current topics from various geographic and pedagogical perspectives. We begin with a Letter to the Editor that presents a critical reflection on contemporary teaching methods, questioning the balance between tradition and innovation in today's language classrooms. In the Inside the Classroom section, we explore the value of brain breaks as tools for improving students' focus, energy, and overall learning experience in language education.

In our Interview section, we delve into the experience of an American professor teaching Spanish in the United States, who discusses the cultural and pedagogical challenges of teaching a foreign language in one's native country. Meanwhile, in our International Corner, three accounts invite us to broaden our global perspective: a native English-speaking teacher reflects on their experience teaching in a Southeast Asian country, highlighting the intercultural dynamics that shape classroom practices; an overview of French language teaching in Chile examines the current role and positioning of French within the local educational landscape; and, finally, a Brazilian professor shares his insights on teaching Portuguese in Chile, offering a rich perspective on the expansion of this language and its cultural relevance in the Latin American context.

This volume reaffirms our commitment to a language education that is critical, context-aware, and globally connected. We hope that the contributions featured in this issue will inspire pedagogical reflection, promote interdisciplinary dialogue, and contribute to the ongoing development of our community of language and culture educators.

Virginie Delalande

*Vice-Rector for Outreach and Public Engagement
(Vinculación con el Medio)*

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Letter to the editor

**Pía
Hidalgo**

Pía

is an English teacher, graduated from Universidad Santo Tomás. From the beginning of her professional journey, she has felt a deep commitment to education, teacher development, and creating meaningful learning experiences for her students. Throughout her career, she has actively sought opportunities to grow both academically and professionally, which has led her to take part in a wide range of teacher training courses, workshops, and educational initiatives.

In June 2024, she was honored to take on the role of Academic Coordinator at the Instituto Chileno Norteamericano, where she has had the opportunity to lead and develop English programs for adults, teens, and children. In this role, she has been responsible for observing and mentoring teachers, preparing and delivering teacher development workshops, and participating in the creation and approval of SENCE courses for that institute.

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Dear Editor,

As a representative of the coordinating area at the Instituto Chileno Norteamericano, I would like to share some reflections on the current landscape of English language teaching, grounded in our experience working with learners of all levels and backgrounds.

In recent years, there has been a clear shift in methodology towards more student-centered, communicative approaches. Techniques such as Communicative Language Teaching (CLT), Task-Based Learning (TBL), and Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL) have proven to be highly effective and well-received by students. These methodologies prioritize meaningful communication over rote memorization, focusing on real-life tasks and authentic use of language. Learners are encouraged to take risks, express themselves freely, and use English as a tool for interaction, rather than viewing it as a subject to be mastered in isolation. What we have found to be particularly successful is the creation of a safe and encouraging environment where students feel comfortable making mistakes. This is essential, as language acquisition is not a linear process—it involves experimentation, error, reflection, and gradual improvement. When students feel supported and not judged, their confidence grows, and they become more willing to participate actively and authentically.

However, the path is not without its challenges. Teachers often struggle to meet the diverse needs of students within the same classroom, and students can feel overwhelmed by the pressure to perform or by the fear of making mistakes. In our experience, the key to overcoming these barriers lies in continuous professional development for teachers and fostering academic self-awareness in students. Teachers must be equipped not only with strong methodological foundations but also with strategies for differentiation, emotional intelligence, and classroom management. At the same time, students benefit from clear guidance on how to take ownership of their learning and view mistakes as an integral part of the journey. At Instituto Chileno Norteamericano,

we strive to strike a balance between structure and flexibility, ensuring that learners build a solid grammatical foundation while also developing fluency and confidence. The incorporation of digital tools, project-based assessments, and reflective practice has significantly enriched the learning experience and aligned it more closely with students' real-world needs.

In conclusion, the most effective methodologies are those that humanize the learning process—where teachers guide, support, and challenge students to use English as a means of communication, not perfection. Encouraging students to speak, even imperfectly, is not just a teaching strategy—it's a philosophy that acknowledges the true nature of language learning. After all, it is through trial, error, and authentic use that we truly grow.

Sincerely,
Pía Hidalgo Aranda

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Matías
Donoso Wright

➔ Matías

has been an English teacher since 2016, currently working at San Gennaro's school, where he teaches English to secondary students. He holds a Master's degree in Neuroscience for Education from Universidad Mayor. Additionally, he teaches at UBO's Instituto de Lenguas Extranjeras y Culturas. His interests focus on the brain processes involved in students' learning. He is also interested in developing motivational strategies for his students during each lesson. He always encourages his students to learn from their mistakes.

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Attention span range per age:

- **Children (5-7 years old):** At this stage, children have relatively short attention spans, typically ranging from 10 to 15 minutes on a single task before becoming distracted (Firth & Riddell, 2020). This is because their cognitive development is still maturing, and they often require frequent breaks or task changes to maintain engagement.
- **Children (8-10 years old):** By this age, children can generally focus for 20 to 30 minutes on a single task, particularly if the activity is engaging or incorporates hands-on learning (Firth & Riddell, 2020). While they are more capable of sustained attention, distractions such as social interactions or media are still significant challenges.
- **Adolescents (11-14 years old):** As children transition into adolescence, their attention span improves, and they can focus for approximately 30 to 40 minutes on average. However, increased exposure to digital media and multitasking can interfere with their ability to concentrate on a single task (Loh & Kanai, 2016).
- **Adolescents (15-16+ years old):** Older adolescents tend to have attention spans of about 45 minutes to an hour, but they still face challenges in environments that demand sustained focus, especially if they are frequently interrupted by technological distractions (Loh & Kanai, 2016). Their ability to focus increases with maturity, but it can be significantly affected by external factors such as media and social interactions.

Understanding the attention span of different age groups is crucial for developing strategies that support learning, productivity, and overall well-being during each lesson. Adjusting expectations and approaches to fit developmental stages can significantly enhance focus and performance in both educational and professional settings.

What are the most effective brain breaks for relaxation?

Based on my experience, some of the most effective brain break strategies for students with boundless energy include

Inside the Classroom

LET'S TAKE A BREAK?

Attentional periods are different according to each student's age. For this reason, it is important to consider this at the moment of planning our classes. Brain breaks are short, purposeful pauses during classroom activities that help students recharge and refocus. These breaks, lasting just a few minutes, can include stretching, deep breathing, or quick physical activities to refresh the mind and body. By incorporating brain breaks, we can boost student attention, reduce restlessness, and promote overall well-being, making learning more effective.

Attention span tends to evolve with age, largely influenced by developmental factors and environmental stimuli. For children and adolescents, research indicates that the duration of sustained attention changes as they grow.

relaxation pauses or breathing activities while listening to or watching relaxing videos on YouTube. Mindful breathing activates the parasympathetic nervous system, reduces cortisol levels, and induces relaxation (Tang, Hölzel, & Posner, 2015). Viewing beautiful landscapes has powerful effects in the brain and body, activating neural pathways associated with pleasure and relaxation, and reducing activity in the stress response system. Neuroscience research shows that looking at natural landscapes can activate the reward system in the brain, especially the prefrontal cortex and the ventral striatum, regions that are associated with positive feelings and motivation (Berto, 2014).

Recommended relaxation activities.

- 1. Drawing or coloring:** Draw or color something simple (e.g., a mandalas) while listening to relaxing music, which could be from a playlist created for this purpose.
- 2. Heartbeat:** Ask students to close their eyes and place their hand on their chest so they can feel their heartbeat. Have them count their beats. This activity is a perfect transition from a dynamic activity to a relaxing one.
- 3. Four Breathing activity:** Ask your students to sit correctly

in their seats. Instruct them to take a deep breath for 4 seconds, hold their breath 4 seconds, exhale slowly for 4 seconds, pause 4 seconds and then repeat. Repeat this activity 3-5 times. You can play some relaxing music (e.g., nature sounds).

4. 4-7-8 breathing: Ask your students to sit comfortably and correctly in their seats. Ask them to close their eyes. They inhale quietly through their nose for 4 seconds. Have the students hold their breath for 7 seconds, then exhale completely and audibly through their mouth for 8 seconds.

5. Watch & breathe: Play relaxing music with natural landscapes and ask students to imagine they are in that place.

6. Guess the sounds: Play some nature sounds and have students recognize them. Encourage them to use their imagination by creating hypothetical situations (e.g., a rainy day).

Exposing students to 5 -7 minutes of this kind of activities, helps them to reduce stress levels and increases the attentional focus.

On the other hand, if your goal is to energize students, reinforce specific lesson content or review for a test, you should consider including some of the activities listed below. Be sure to take into account the age range of the students to include enough brain breaks during your lesson.

Top 10 brain break activities

1. **Bingo:** You can create a bingo card on the student's notebook to reinforce vocabulary from the class or any topic that motivates students (music, literature, video games, etc).
2. **Dance party:** 2-3 minutes dance session to energize the class (e.g., Just Dance videos)
3. **Simon says:** a fun, attention-based game that involves listening and responding quickly.
4. **Brain teasers:** Short, interactive puzzles, word searches or riddles.
5. **Telephone:** share a story with the class and have them pass it along to see how it changes.
6. **Karaoke:** Create a class playlist and play one song during your pause. Students sing and read the lyrics.
7. **Clap for call and response:** Clap out a pattern that pupils will repeat back to you (you can search for different patterns on YouTube or social media).
8. **Charades:** Students guess a concept by acting it out without speaking. The class then guesses the concept or idea.
9. **Freeze dance:** Play some upbeat music and have students dance. When the music stops, they must freeze in place. This is a fun way to get them moving and focused again.
10. **Animal walks:** Lead the class in moving like different animals:

hop like a frog, slither like a snake, or waddle like a penguin.

I advise other teachers to create their own bank of activation activities; you can tailor them to specific subjects, grades, and classroom environments. This flexibility allows for more dynamic, responsive teaching. With a variety of activities at your fingertips, you can easily incorporate them into your lesson plans to boost student engagement and improve learning outcomes. Additionally, having a well-stocked activity bank ensures that you are always prepared to meet the diverse needs of your students and at the same time, saves you time in planning.

Incorporating brain breaks into the classroom has proven to be a game-changer for both students and teachers alike. From my perspective, these short, intentional pauses not only boost students' focus and engagement, but they also promote emotional well-being and reduce stress. By giving students the opportunity to move, reset, and reconnect, brain breaks allow them to return to their tasks with more energy and a clearer mindset. As a teacher, I've witnessed firsthand how these breaks foster a positive classroom environment, where students are more eager to participate, collaborate, and retain the material being taught. Finally, brain breaks are not just a tool for academic success, but an essential part of cultivating a balanced and supportive learning experience.

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An interview with

Becoming a Spanish professor in the North American Midwest

BACKGROUND AND EXPERIENCE

1. Why did you choose to become a Spanish teacher? Did you have a prior connection with the language?

This is a good question! I am not quite sure how I fell in to being a Spanish teacher, but two things come to mind.

First, when I was a child, I loved languages even though they were not taught in my elementary school. I bought books to try to learn Spanish and German. My next-door neighbor was from Costa Rica and my parents had friends from Switzerland. When I got to 8th grade, I was thrilled to finally be able to take a course in Spanish and loved it. I am not sure why I inherently liked languages, but I always enjoyed reading and verbal things, so it was a natural evolution to be interested in languages. Also, I was always interested in getting to know people from other countries, even though I didn't have many international classmates.

Second, when I was at university, I kept taking Spanish courses and realized that studying the language was more than verb conjugation and grammar. I took courses from professors who taught students about culture, history, current events, literature, art, and film. I think it was the interdisciplinary nature of the courses that deepened my interest in studying Spanish. When I was close to graduating from the university, a few of my professors convinced me to keep going, to pursue a master's degree in Spanish. I figured it was only two years, and I was young so I might as well continue. Most graduate programs in the United States were and are heavily focused on literature and cultural

Julie Stephens
de Jonge

Julie

PhD, is a professor of Spanish at the University of Central Missouri in the United States. She teaches a range of courses including language, literature, film, and civilization courses. She has published a textbook to learn Spanish based on short films, articles on digital escape rooms, and a textbook on Spanish Civilization with TopHat.com that includes interviews and interactive activities. She is interested in the scholarship of teaching and learning about teaching critical thinking, stories to frame ethical topics, and game-based education.

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studies rather than linguistics. I wasn't sure if learning about those aspects of a language would translate into a job or a career, but I really enjoyed learning a lot of new things, new ways of understanding society, people, culture etc. so again I just kept going when the opportunity to pursue the PhD came up. The PhD program did take a while—about five years. In retrospect, it was probably a bit too long. It delayed me getting a full-time job and I had very little money during that time. But, once I was into the doctoral program, I wanted to finish. When I finally got the degree and went out into the job market, I realized that most of the jobs would not involve teaching the subjects I had spent so much time learning in graduate school. Most colleges and universities wanted professors to focus on more pragmatic language development. But for me, that has been okay. I really enjoy teaching both languages and other disciplines in the humanities. I love that teaching language is so interdisciplinary. I can include so many topics, even in a traditional language class.

2. What levels (beginner, intermediate, advanced) have you taught, and which do you prefer? Why? Can you mention a challenge of teaching on each level?

I teach all levels offered at the university.

Beginner: One challenge at this level is that students are often not motivated, and they underestimate how much effort and time is required to attain proficiency. Once they realize how difficult it is to reach a level of fluency, they become discouraged and often decide not to keep taking a language.

Intermediate: I think motivation is an issue with this level. Once they realize the difficulty of becoming proficient, some students decide they cannot continue or do not want to continue.

Advanced: I love teaching advanced students, but they still need encouragement and confidence building. One challenge is sometimes they feel they have “mastered” everything but really haven’t, and need more practice.

TEACHING METHODS AND PHILOSOPHY

3. What teaching methodologies do you find most effective for teaching Spanish as a second language?

I like to combine some explanation / direct teaching of the language along with practice that is appropriate to the students’ level. Even though some language

instructors say you should never explain or go over grammar, I find that for adult learners, it is still an important part of the process. Language learning involves multiple skills and although they reinforce each other, second language learners still need explicit knowledge (as opposed to implicit knowledge) of the language. There are many people, for example, in the US whose first language is not English. Even though they have been here for many years, they still cannot speak the language. I think that they lack the instruction and understanding of the language to become more proficient.

I try to lean in to humor, mystery, games, and other information to capture student interest. I think it’s important to mix things up, not do the same thing every day. I want the students to do a bit of everything: simple activities and more difficult ones, writing activities, individual activities, challenges, and something fun. I also believe strongly in the power of visual

input, whether it is an image or a video. Humans are very oriented toward the visual and students today are even more “impatient” with things that are text only. To the extent that something can be made visual, I think it is important to do so.

4. How do you incorporate cultural aspects of Spanish-speaking countries into your lessons? What aspects of the Spanish speaking world do you incorporate in your classes? Why are they important to be taught?

Culture is so vast, so hard to define, and yet paradoxically important. I try not to teach culture in a fragmented way. I don’t want it to be like a collage of unrelated information. I prefer to have some sort of cultural input that allows students to explore cultural knowledge more organically. For example, I teach the Chilean film, *No hay pan*, about a business owner whose “*almacén*” is threatened by the arrival of a supermarket.

This gives us the pretext to talk about what an “*almacén*” is, how the concept of “*regatear*” works in many cultures and even to start by looking for Chile on a map.

In general, I think instructors should work to define what they mean when they talk about “teaching” culture. Certainly, teaching facts, basic knowledge is important; students do need to know about basic geography or history, for example. But beyond that, what are the goals? Can cultural information be incorporated into an effort to improve critical thinking, for example? If so, how? In general, I think teaching culture has not been sufficiently critically examined. Instructors say it's important, but what aspect? What pieces of information? How does culture fit into larger goals of creating global citizens or engendering curiosity?

5. Can you describe a typical lesson plan or classroom activity you use? Is there any specific strategy you use to keep students engaged and motivated during lessons?

I like to start class with an interesting question, a puzzle, or an activity to warm them up. Sometimes I just ask an A or B question. I might work with vocabulary and ask students if they prefer “A” or “B” and have them point to the left or the right to indicate their preference. This allows them to do something “simple” at the beginning of class but still engages them with the topic. Then I usually do about 10-15 minutes of direct instruction, either of a language concept or something cultural. After the direct instruction, I present something relatively easy for them to practice whatever we went over. Then, I would ask students to produce or work with the content that has been presented.

6. How do you adapt your teaching strategies for students with different learning styles or special needs?

I try to assume that every student needs extra support or what we call, scaffolding,

in the classroom. The more prepared students still benefit from scaffolding but the students who might need more support feel more included. I think it's important to vary the activities in class. I like group / paired / peer activities, but not all students feel comfortable working with others. Even though students should learn to work with others, I try to provide opportunities for students to engage with the material in their own way. Activities that allow students to receive immediate feedback, without negative consequences, are an effective, low-stakes way to increase their confidence, and therefore, engagement.

CLASSROOM MANAGEMENT

7. How do you handle language barriers in the classroom, especially with beginner students?

I try hard to balance challenging activities with easy ones. I use English when necessary to reduce anxiety. I am not sure that using L2 100% of the time works. I have always read / heard that that is what language teachers are supposed to do. But it has never quite felt right to me. Maybe that works with exceptional or very motivated students. I try to ease students into hearing and working with Spanish only. I think we have to start with emotions, which means building confidence and making people want to continue. Without that, it won't matter what we do.

8. What strengths and weaknesses can you mention about yourself as a teacher?

One of my weaknesses is feeling a bit reluctant to push or challenge students. I sometimes think I could have found a way to challenge students more than I do. Another weakness is figuring out how to give less positive feedback. I would like to do better with more constructive feedback. I enjoy giving positive feedback (good job!) but still struggle with how to give more effective, “negative” feedback.

Lastly, another weakness is not articulating better the learning objectives to students. I believe being transparent about what we want to achieve in class and why we are doing what we are doing is helpful. I should do more of that.

I also think my experience is a weakness. I have been teaching a long time and it's easy to get into habits or into a rut with the way I do things. I wonder if maybe I am missing some strategies that might be effective. For that reason, I really enjoy and benefit from hearing from other instructors and their insights. I believe we always have to have an attitude that we can and should learn from others and do better.

I think my strengths are an ability to engage effectively on an interpersonal level with every student. I also think because I am always thinking about creative interventions with students that my lessons and classes generally have something engaging.

ASSESSMENT AND FEEDBACK

9. How do you provide feedback to students on their language skills?

I like to encourage students to make errors and then correct them with no grade penalty. I have become a proponent of the “ungrading” movement, which gives students more ownership of their learning and rewards them for meeting high standards but gives them multiple opportunities to meet those standards.

I also believe strongly in positive feedback. I believe students sort of shut down when faced with harsh or very direct criticism.

CHALLENGES AND REWARDS

10. What challenges have you faced in teaching Spanish, and how have you overcome them?

Overall, I think teaching has two big challenges: 1) motivating students and figuring out what strategies and activities make sense for the learning objective.

To motivate students, I try to create an environment and activities that build confidence. Without confidence, students naturally retreat mentally. Once they have decided that “languages are not for them”, it doesn't matter how clever or engaging the class is, they will have opted to not engage. Balancing more challenging activities with something “simple” gives students the sense that they are still grasping some of the foundational concepts.

Figuring out what “works” is partially a trial and error process. I have tried many activities that I decide later did not work. On the other hand, I have created some activities that seemed to really appeal to the students. That type of feedback, even if it is informal, motivates me to continue to use those activities.

11. What do you find most rewarding about teaching Spanish as a second language?

I love teaching in general and I love language. I really enjoying figuring out how to present information in an effective way. I like thinking about how to structure lessons that resonate with the students and allow them to improve.

TECHNOLOGY AND RESOURCES

12. How do you integrate technology into your lessons? Are there specific tools or resources you recommend?

I love a lot of ed tech resources online. I like to use technology that students perceive as fun or engaging. I believe PowerPoint or presentation software in general still has a role in direct instruction, but I think instructors should learn more about presentation strategies and effective slides. For example, information should be animated in and students should not have to read large walls of text.

As far as engaging, fun tech in the classroom I like: Blooket.com, breakoutedu.com, flippity.com, Kahoot.com, PowerPoint (for games like “Riesgo”), Plickers.com and all Google tools because they are linkable.

PERSONAL EXPERIENCE AND INSIGHTS

13. What advice would you give to someone who is just starting to learn Spanish?

There are many pieces of advice but to start, I would suggest committing to practice and learning for short periods of time, but frequently. I think people are more likely to stick with something if they know they can make progress in 10-15 minutes / day. Frequency, not so much length of time doing something, seems to be more powerful. Language learning involves so much memorization, and I believe instructors and students underestimate how much exposure students need with vocabulary to acquire words. Students would benefit from very frequent exposure, even if it is a short period of time. Also, it is very important to engage in “retrieval practice”, which means quizzing yourself. There is a lot of evidence in learning science that students benefit more from quizzing themselves rather than reviewing notes or rereading. Students need to try to recall information.

CLOSING

14. Is there anything else you would like to share about your experiences or philosophy in teaching Spanish as a second language?

I love teaching language because it interface with so many other disciplines, in the arts, in social sciences, literature, film etc. Languages are a portal into other worlds and other ways of thinking about human problems, human experiences, and human endeavors in general. I think I have tried to always take a bigger picture approach to teaching. Students will forget details. For example, they may forget how to conjugate certain verbs. That is inevitable. But I hope I can teach things in a way that leaves them with a memory of something interesting, a fascinating question, or just a “gist” about something that proves to be important or relevant to them in their lives. I think instructors always aspire to have an impact. That impact is more likely to be achieved when we infuse teaching with something emotional, with a sense of purpose, and meaning.

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EFL Teachers' Perceptions on Teaching Students Within the Autistic Spectrum Disorder

The inclusion of students with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) in English as a Foreign Language (EFL) classrooms in Chile is a challenge due to a lack of resources and teacher training. Despite international and national programs, there are significant gaps to support EFL teachers to work with ASD students. A qualitative study of three EFL teachers revealed that despite their efforts, teachers face significant barriers due to a lack of specialized tools and adequate institutional support. The study suggests the need for public policies promoting an inclusive approach in the Chilean educational curriculum

Introduction

Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) students often face significant learning challenges, particularly in comprehension and social skills, which significantly impact their academic performance. These difficulties present significant barriers for educators, making it difficult to design and implement inclusive lessons that effectively engage all students. In Chile, many schools opt to exclude ASD students from English classes without developing action plans, working together with the school community, or seeking practical solutions from the "Programa de Integración Escolar" (PIE) to provide support to teachers.

Autism is one of the best known special educational needs

This is an abridged version of the article. However, the references from the original paper have been kept for further study

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(SEN), causing persistent difficulties in social communication and interactions across various contexts. People with ASD often face challenges in social interaction and relatedness, contrary to the assumption that autism is defined only by an inability to socialize. Cognitively, people with ASD exhibit problems related to language processing, communicative production, and repetitive behavior, which are cognitive skills that they usually do not have.

ASD is categorized into three levels based on the support required: Level 1 (help needed), Level 2 (significant help needed), and Level 3 (very significant help needed). Children with autism typically require specialized educational approaches rather than merely tools to assist them in basic social, communication, and reasoning skills. This includes using graphic or visual materials to establish classroom norms or provide instructions.

Teachers should be more aware when developing classes for students with Special Educational Needs (SEN) and receive adequate training to enhance their sense of self-efficacy. PIE helps with school integration and works collaboratively with teachers to provide support to the student who needs it. However, English teachers often find themselves without adequate support when addressing the specific needs of ASD students, leading to their exclusion from class activities.

General Objective

To analyze the perceptions of the teachers interviewed in this research about students with Autism Spectrum (ASD) in English classes.

Specific Objectives

1. To determine the previous teaching training experiences of the interviewed teachers in this research with Autism Spectrum students.
2. To analyze strategies that the interviewed teachers use to carry out an English class with ASD students.
3. To determine the possible challenges that the interviewed teachers have faced when teaching ASD students.

Research questions:

1. What is the teaching training that the interviewed teachers have received regarding ASD students?
2. What are the strategies that the interviewed teachers use in their classes when teaching ASD students?
3. What are the challenges that the interviewed teachers have encountered when teaching ASD students?

Literature review

This Literature Review explores research on teaching students with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) in English as a Foreign Language (EFL) settings, emphasizing the challenges teachers face, instructional strategies used, and the importance of inclusive classrooms. It highlights the need to further investigate teachers' perceptions and the sufficiency of their training in meeting ASD students' needs. English's linguistic features may aid ASD students in acquiring the language more quickly (Hashim et al., 2021). In Chile, limited time and teacher shortages hinder individualized instruction, requiring educators to be flexible and to use engaging multimedia tools like books, puzzles, videos, and audio to maintain motivation and focus (Maysuroh et al., 2024).

Chile's Programa de Integración Escolar (PIE) supports educational inclusion by offering pedagogical strategies and interdisciplinary evaluations from specialists to meet students' learning needs (MINEDUC, 2016). The review also clarifies the distinction between inclusion and integration. Inclusion, as defined by UNESCO (2023), ensures all students receive quality education tailored to their needs, emphasizing full participation through methods such as multimodal instruction and collaborative learning. Integration, by contrast, is described by Romero & Lauretti (2006) as a process starting from the family, focusing on incorporating students with special educational needs (SEN) into academic and social life through environmental adaptations and support. Romero & Venegas (2024) argue that inclusion seeks to eliminate barriers by gathering and evaluating diverse information to guide improvements. While both concepts aim for equitable student participation, inclusion goes further in fostering emotional development and a respectful, diverse classroom environment (Fernández as cited in González and Triana, 2018). Ultimately, the teacher plays a pivotal role in ensuring these inclusive and integrative goals are met.

Many English teachers feel unprepared to teach students with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) due to insufficient training during their higher education. This often leads them to rely on workshops or trial-and-error strategies (Morrier et al., 2011). Historically, neurodivergent students were frequently overlooked in the classroom, with some English teachers opting to pass them on without ensuring learning had occurred. However, current expectations emphasize the need for ongoing professional development for teachers (Medina de Armas, Marquez, & Martínez, 2021), as well-trained educators are essential for quality education (UNESCO, 2023).

Training programs for English teachers in higher education often

lack adequate focus on inclusion and support for neurodiverse students. For example, Universidad Católica de Chile includes only one subject related to inclusion—Diversity and Inclusion in Education—in the third year (Universidad Católica de Chile, 2024). Universidad Diego Portales offers TEFL Methodology: Diversity and Inclusion during the same academic year, but only for one semester, prioritizing strategies for neurotypical students instead (Universidad Diego Portales, 2024). Universidad Autónoma de Chile provides a more comprehensive curriculum: beginning in the first year with Neuroeducation in the Classroom, which integrates brain-based teaching methods (Meneses, 2019), and continuing with Learning for Diversity, integration workshops, and Inclusive Approaches in English Language Pedagogy in later years (Universidad Autónoma de Chile, 2024). This institution's curriculum underscores the value of inclusive education and the teacher's role in addressing all learners' needs.

According to Brahim (2022), all learners with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) face language and communication difficulties, making English as a Foreign Language (EFL) instruction challenging. Gałązka and Dick-Bursztyn (2019, as cited in Brahim, 2022) emphasize the importance of tailoring language teaching to learners' preferences. Carefully designed lesson plans are essential for ASD learners. Manti, Scholte, and Van Berckelaer-Onnes (2012, as cited in Murray, 2015) found that appropriate education enhances academic, social, and communication skills in children

with ASD.

Differentiated instruction is highlighted as an effective strategy (Brahim, 2022), with Murray (2015) supporting the integration of technology, structured environments, and adapted reading activities. Social strategies, crucial for learners who struggle with imitation and interpreting cues (Jacklin & Farr, 2005), should be taught in relevant environments (Fleury et al., 2014). Ostmeyer and Scarpa (2012) point out that skills learned at school may not easily transfer to other settings. Peer modeling, playful imitation, and technology are effective tools for enhancing social interaction (Murray, 2015; Jacklin & Farr, 2005; Field et al., 2008).

Behavioral challenges, such as difficulty following rules or repetitive actions, can disrupt learning (Ostmeyer & Scarpa, 2012). Fleury et al. (2014) suggest using instructional and behavioral supports, while Boyd et al. (2011, as cited in Murray, 2015) found ERP interventions helpful. Technology, such as iPads, has reduced disruptive behaviors and improved engagement (Neely et al., 2013; Perfit, 2013). To support transitions, visual schedules and student involvement in planning are recommended (Perfit, 2013; Murray, 2015).

Academic strategies like using technology, shared reading, and structured learning environments are essential (Murray, 2015). Visual tools and individualized reading improve comprehension (Muchetti, 2013, as cited in Fleury et al., 2014; Murray, 2015), while step-by-step instruction helps with executive functioning deficits (Fleury et al., 2014; Murray, 2015). Structured classrooms reduce anxiety and promote learning (Manti et al., 2012; Murray, 2015).

The term methodology refers to the approaches and techniques that teachers use to enhance student learning, and these have evolved alongside educational developments, shifting from traditional methods to incorporating games and technology to improve educational quality and knowledge acquisition. Sulca (2021) cited Casillas (2015) in defining the traditional pedagogical model as one that preserves the existing order through a teacher-centered approach, where the teacher holds authority and knowledge is transmitted verbally, leading students to adopt passive, memorization-based learning behaviors. In contrast, cooperative learning engages students in small groups to foster peer-supported learning and constructive interaction (Johnson, Johnson, and Holubec, 2008 as cited in Buchs, 2017). The Montessori Method, as described by Montessori M. (2015, cited in Álvarez, 2021), emphasizes individual development, promoting independence and self-directed learning through interaction with carefully designed materials. Gamification, as explained by Parente (cited in Ruth, 2016), involves applying video game design elements such as rewards and levels to education, thereby maintaining motivation and engagement through gameplay mechanics. Lastly, the competency approach, particularly prevalent in Chilean schools offering Differentiated Technical-Professional Training (EMTP), centers on developing practical and applicable skills for both professional and personal adult life (retrieved from MINEDUC, 2016).

Education must emphasize both equality and equity to support

students with disabilities, especially those with autism spectrum disorder (ASD), whose unique needs require tailored educational approaches (Brahim, 2022; Padmadewi & Artini, 2017). Students with ASD often face challenges in communication and social interaction, making it essential to design teaching materials that address these difficulties (Brahim, 2022). Instruction should be individualized, reflecting each student's preferences and needs to promote inclusion and understanding (Gałazka & Dick-Bursztyn, 2019). Visual tools are particularly effective for students with ASD, as they tend to be visual learners and benefit from images and graphics that enhance comprehension and retention (Gladfelter et al., 2019; Brahim, 2022). Differentiated instruction is another important strategy, allowing educators to meet diverse student needs through tailored support (Ford, 2013; Brahim, 2022). Additionally, social stories help students with ASD understand social situations and improve interpersonal skills (Ghanouni et al., 2018; Brahim, 2022). Collaboration with specialists and parents further ensures that teaching approaches are well-suited to these students' needs.

English teachers often face significant challenges when teaching students with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD), primarily due to a lack of knowledge about how to effectively support them in the classroom. As Rangel (2017) notes, inclusion introduces new educational challenges that require diverse methodological approaches tailored to individual learning needs, often within inflexible curricula. When institutional expectations are not met, teachers may feel frustrated and unsuccessful. A major challenge in English classrooms is encouraging interaction between ASD students and others, especially during speaking activities, which is difficult given these students often experience communication and social interaction difficulties, along with repetitive behavioral patterns (Yáñez, B., Saltos, C., Mendoza, R., Loor, C., & Rojas, D., 2024).

Successful inclusion requires patience and dedication, with an understanding that communication with neurodiverse students must be built gradually. Visual aids are often necessary to help ASD students transform abstract concepts into concrete ideas, aiding memory, emotional regulation, and social skills such as empathy and communication (Bachelor in Educational Inclusion, 2018).

Another persistent issue is the lack of preparation at the university level for teaching English to ASD students. According to Maldonado (2024), while educational institutions support individual and social development, they often fail to provide sufficient training on inclusion and integration. This results in teachers feeling unprepared, especially emotionally. The frustration of not achieving full inclusion stems from a lack of practice, tools, and training (Maldonado, 2024), and discrimination continues to limit access to inclusive education. Emotional and attitudinal factors are crucial in language acquisition, and a teacher's negative emotions can hinder learning (Krashen, S., 1998, as cited in Hernández, I., Quiñones, S., 2023). Therefore, teachers must adapt their methods, manage their emotions, and use didactic materials to support ASD students in acquiring English. These materials not

only enhance student engagement and skill development but also help teachers assess learning progress (Arteaga, S. et al., 2024).

The "Programa de Integración Escolar" (PIE) is an inclusive initiative by Chile's Ministry of Education aimed at supporting students with Special Educational Needs (SEN), whether permanent or temporary, to promote their full participation in the classroom.

Methodology

Type of research

This study used a qualitative methodology to deeply explore the perceptions of educators experienced in teaching students with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD). Qualitative research, as described by Sampieri (2014), enables flexibility in refining questions and generating new insights during interpretation, making it suitable for understanding complex realities. It also allows researchers to capture individuals' experiences and opinions about specific phenomena in context.

Research design

The study employs a phenomenological research design to investigate teachers' perceptions of their experiences with students with ASD. This approach is ideal for examining lived experiences and aims to provide deeper insight into the phenomenon.

The study employed non-probabilistic purposive sampling to select participants based on their relevant experiences, specifically targeting EFL teachers who have worked with students with ASD. This sampling method emphasizes selecting individuals not by chance, but due to their specific characteristics aligned with the research goals (Sampieri, 2014). The sample included three participants who were willing to share their experiences teaching English to students with ASD.

Ethical considerations

This study involves collecting personal data from human participants, requiring adherence to ethical standards that protect their rights and well-being (Jiménez, 2008). Participants were required to sign a written consent form outlining the study's purpose, ethical considerations, and participant profile. Key ethical principles include voluntary participation, anonymity, data non-traceability, and full disclosure of the study's scope and potential benefits. Participants were also guaranteed access to more information, the freedom to withdraw at any time without consequences, and researcher impartiality regarding their responses.

Instrument

The study utilized a semi-structured interview with open-ended questions to gather participants' perceptions of teaching English as a foreign language (EFL) to students with ASD. Interviews lasted 45 minutes to 1 hour and were conducted via Google Meet. A preliminary interview matrix was created to guide the development of the open-ended questions, serving as the final instrument

for data collection. This approach helped focus on participants' experiences, aiming to understand common phenomena shared among them (Creswell, 2007). The semi-structured format was deemed appropriate as it allowed for flexibility in exploring unanticipated responses and obtaining more specific information beyond the pre-planned questions.

Data analysis

This study uses thematic analysis to examine the data collected, focusing on the subjective perceptions of interviewees. The analysis follows the steps outlined by Braun and Clarke (2006), starting with the compilation of interview data, followed by the generation of initial codes. The data is then organized into potential themes, reviewed, and refined. Finally, the results are elaborated upon and conclusions are drawn.

Results and Discussion

The following section analyzes semi-structured interviews through thematic analysis, structured around the study's three research questions. It draws on EFL teachers' responses, comparing them with existing literature to better understand their perceptions, beliefs, and practices concerning ASD students in Chile.

1. EFL Teachers' Perceptions Regarding Their Training on Teaching ASD Students

This section explores EFL teachers' perceptions of their training to teach students with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD), focusing on two main themes: limited university training and the need for ongoing support and development.

1.1. Limited ASD Training during University Studies

All three interviewed teachers agreed that their university education offered minimal preparation for teaching students with ASD. Teacher A noted that only one course addressed special educational needs, describing it as insufficient and mostly theoretical: "practice makes perfect" (Teacher A). Similarly, Teacher C criticized the overly broad focus on diversity without specific attention to ASD: "they hardly teach you anything..." (Teacher C). Teacher B emphasized that their knowledge came almost entirely from hands-on experience and peer collaboration: "everything I learned was through practice" (Teacher B).

This lack of preparation is consistent with findings from Chilean university curricula, which typically include only brief and general courses on special education, often lasting less than a semester. Meneses (2019) pointed out that even when subjects like "Neuroeducation in the Classroom" are included, they are limited in scope. These insights reflect a broader issue, as Medina de Armas, Márquez, and Martínez (2021) argue that modern education must involve continuous training. UNESCO (2023, 2024) also emphasizes the need for well-trained and supported teachers to ensure quality education, particularly in inclusive classrooms.

1.2. Need for Ongoing Training and Support in Teaching Students with ASD

Beyond university shortcomings, the teachers highlighted the importance of continuous professional development. All three stressed that ASD remains a relatively new and evolving subject in Chilean education, requiring updated training and practical tools. Teacher B expressed the urgency for universities to prioritize ASD training, stating, "teachers must be adequately trained" (Teacher B). The interviews underscored the value of support networks, especially integration teams, and peer collaboration, in helping teachers adapt their methods. As Medina de Armas et al. (2021) suggest, continuous training allows educators to recycle and update their knowledge, which is vital given the current gaps in university preparation. The teachers called for both more specialized courses during initial training and structured ongoing support to meet the diverse needs of students with ASD.

2. EFL Teachers' Perceptions Regarding the Strategies Used in Teaching ASD Students

This section explores the strategies employed by EFL teachers to support students with autism spectrum disorder (ASD), focusing on classroom adaptations, instructional methods, and individualized support.

2.1 Adaptation Based on Observation

Teachers adapt their methods based on careful observation of student preferences and needs. Teacher A emphasizes observing students to tailor content and maintain routine, minimizing stress (Gałązka & Dick-Bursztyn, 2019 in Brahim, 2022; Murray, 2015). Teacher B prefers oral assessments and simplified yes/no questions to suit younger ASD students, aligning with differentiated instruction practices (Brahim, 2022). Teacher C relies on curricular adaptations and collaboration with specialists, supporting team-based approaches (Boyd et al., 2011). While Teachers A and B focus on classroom-level strategies, Teacher C advocates for structural support through specialist involvement.

2.2 Preference for Practical Activities and Use of Visual Materials

All three teachers favor hands-on activities over traditional assessments to accommodate ASD students' learning styles. Teacher A avoids lengthy worksheets and opts for practical evaluations, which reduce stress and communication challenges (Brahim, 2022; Padmadewi & Artini, 2017). Teacher B incorporates sensory materials like sand and headphones to aid focus and regulate energy, recognizing the importance of visual and tactile tools (Gladfelter et al., 2019; Brahim, 2022). Teacher C emphasizes visual and interactive resources to engage students and support understanding (Gałązka & Dick-Bursztyn, 2019; Brahim, 2022). While each teacher employs different tools, all highlight the importance of differentiated, engaging materials.

2.3 Individualized Support Strategies and Environmental Control

Teachers stress the value of environmental control and individualized support. Teacher A uses tools like a 'traffic light' system to manage noise and promotes diversity awareness, reinforcing inclusive classroom practices (Brahim, 2022). Teacher B supports peer collaboration and independent work tailored to each student, echoing cooperative learning principles (Johnson, Johnson, & Holubec, 2008, as cited in Buchs, 2017). Teacher C emphasizes flexible evaluation and student choice, advocating for Montessori-inspired autonomy and personalized assessment (Montessori, 2015, as cited in Cuevas, 2021). These strategies showcase a range of inclusive methods adapted to students' diverse needs.

3. English Teachers' Perceptions of the Challenges Teaching ASD Students

This section explores the challenges English teachers face when working with students with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD), particularly the need to constantly adapt teaching strategies to accommodate diverse learning needs.

3.1 Constant Changes in Learning Strategies

Teachers report ongoing challenges in adapting their teaching methods to suit ASD students' individual needs. Teacher A highlights the difficulty of encouraging English interaction among ASD students, noting the need for patience and gradual confidence-building:

"The biggest challenge is getting them to interact in English..." (Teacher A).

This aligns with Yáñez et al. (2024), who note that communication difficulties are common in ASD. Visual aids, as outlined in the Licenciatura en Educación Educativa curriculum (2018), are essential for facilitating comprehension and emotional regulation. Teacher B points to the struggle of adjusting pedagogical methods amid large class sizes and insufficient teacher training:

"[...] the biggest challenge I can face is the strategy I use to teach..." (Teacher B).

Rangel (2017) supports the need for varied methodologies, though rigid curricula often hinder their implementation. Maldonado (2024) stresses better university preparation for teachers to support inclusive classrooms.

Teacher C discusses issues related to attention span and varying learning paces:

"[...] the attention of ASD students can be a challenge..." (Teacher C).

This illustrates the importance of personalized instruction, as supported by Yáñez et al. (2024), to accommodate different student rhythms.

All three teachers agree on the need for patience, tailored strategies, and efforts to foster interaction in English. Each emphasizes a different aspect: content personalization (Teacher A), oral

assessments and training gaps (Teacher B), and curriculum adjustments and inter-professional collaboration (Teacher C).

3.2 Interaction, Inclusion, and Collaboration Between Neurotypical and ASD Students in the Classroom

Teachers emphasize the importance of inclusive, respectful environments where ASD and neurotypical students can thrive together. Teacher A notes that younger students benefit from learning about diversity, and teacher attitude is critical for fostering inclusion:

"It impacts the younger students, who learn about diversity and respect..." (Teacher A).

This aligns with UNESCO (2023), which advocates for education systems that respect individual needs.

Teacher B highlights the complementary roles of schools and families:

"[...] school is essential... but I feel it's 80% home..." (Teacher B).

This supports Romero & Lauretti (2006), who argue that inclusion starts within the family and requires joint efforts between school and home.

Teacher C emphasizes how inclusion fosters empathy and teamwork:

"When we include ASD students, all other students learn to be more empathetic..." (Teacher C).

This view is supported by De la Barra and Carbone (2020), who promote the value of cooperative learning and shared goals.

Overall, all teachers stress the importance of school-family collaboration and affirm that inclusive practices benefit both ASD and neurotypical students. As noted by Romero & Venegas (2024) and the Red de Educación Inclusiva (2021), true inclusion involves more than shared space—it requires the removal of social and academic barriers to ensure meaningful participation.

Conclusions

This research aimed to explore EFL teachers' perceptions of teaching students with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) in English classes. It focused on their training, teaching strategies, and the challenges they face. The study found that many teachers feel underprepared due to insufficient university training and limited institutional support, particularly from Chile's Programa de Integración Escolar (PIE). Teachers highlighted the need to adapt materials and methods to meet the diverse needs of ASD students, often using visual aids, hands-on tasks, and personalized assessments.

Despite the difficulties, teachers view inclusion positively, noting its benefits for both ASD and neurotypical students by fostering empathy and collaboration. They stressed the importance of continuous teacher training, strong school-family partnerships, and flexible, supportive learning environments. Ultimately, the study concludes that while current educational policies fall short, effective inclusion requires better preparation, resources, and a shared commitment to understanding and supporting neurodiverse learners.

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International corner

My Journey as an English Teacher in Penang, Malaysia

Introduction

For over 15 years, I have had the incredible opportunity to teach English in the vibrant and culturally rich city of Penang, Malaysia. This journey has not only allowed me to impart knowledge but also to grow personally and professionally. Additionally, I have had the privilege of conducting teacher training programs and working as a speaking examiner, which has further enriched my experience.

Challenges

Teaching English in Penang has come with its unique set of challenges. One of the primary hurdles has been the language barrier. While many students have a basic understanding of English, their proficiency levels vary significantly. This disparity often requires tailored teaching approaches to ensure that each student can progress at their own pace.

Cultural adjustments have also been a significant aspect of my journey. Understanding and respecting the local customs and traditions have been crucial in building a rapport with my students and their families. For instance, being mindful of religious practices and holidays has helped me create a more inclusive and respectful learning environment.

Teaching Methodologies

Over the years, I have developed and refined various teaching methodologies to cater to the diverse needs of my students. Interactive and communicative approaches have proven to be particularly effective. By incorporating group activities, role-plays, and real-life scenarios, I have been able to make learning more engaging and practical.

Technology has also played a pivotal role in my teaching methods. Utilizing multimedia resources, online platforms, and language learning apps has made lessons more dynamic and accessible. These tools have been especially beneficial in bridging the gap between different proficiency levels and keeping students motivated.

Language Barriers

Language barriers have been a persistent challenge, but they have also provided valuable learning opportunities. To overcome these barriers, I have employed various strategies such as visual aids, simplified language, and consistent reinforcement. Encouraging students to practice speaking in a safe and supportive environment has also been crucial in building their confidence and fluency.

Cultural Adjustments

Adapting to the local culture has been an enriching experience. Penang's multicultural environment has exposed me to a blend of Malay, Chinese, and Indian traditions. Embracing this diversity has not only enhanced my teaching but also broadened my cultural understanding. Participating in local festivals, trying traditional foods, and learning basic phrases in Malay and other local languages have helped me connect with my students on a deeper level.

Personal Growth

My time in Penang has been a period of immense personal growth. Living and working in a foreign country has taught me resilience, adaptability, and empathy. I have learned to navigate new environments, build relationships across cultural boundaries, and appreciate the beauty of diversity.

Conducting teacher training programs has been particularly rewarding. Sharing my knowledge and experiences with fellow educators has allowed me to contribute to the professional development of others. It has also provided me with fresh perspectives and innovative ideas that I have incorporated into my own teaching practice.

Conclusion

Teaching English in Penang, Malaysia, for over 15 years has been a transformative journey. The challenges, cultural adjustments, and personal growth I have experienced have shaped me into a more effective and empathetic educator. As I continue to teach and train others, I am grateful for the opportunity to make a positive impact on my students' lives and to be part of such a vibrant and diverse community.

Emilie Béland

Emilie

est responsable du Centre d'Employabilité Francophone (CEF) de l'Université Bernardo O'Higgins. Elle est titulaire d'un baccalauréat en communication de l'Université de Sherbrooke et d'une maîtrise en sciences politiques de l'Université de Montréal, au Canada. Emilie vit au Chili depuis 15 ans et a travaillé dans différentes organisations gouvernementales et de la société civile avant de s'intégrer à l'UBO.

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Le coin international

Le français au Chili : d'un passé glorieux à de nouvelles opportunités dans un monde hispanophone

Au Chili, jusqu'à la fin des années 1990, le français était enseigné comme langue seconde dans de nombreux établissements publics et privés. La langue de Molière bénéficiait d'un statut privilégié, hérité d'un passé où la culture française faisait figure de modèle intellectuel et artistique. Mais depuis quelques décennies, le paysage linguistique chilien a changé. Si le français n'est plus aussi dominant, il reste cependant loin d'être relégué au rang des langues mortes. Mieux encore, il connaît aujourd'hui un certain renouveau, porté par des opportunités professionnelles, académiques et culturelles nouvelles.

Un prestige d'antan : le français comme langue seconde jusqu'aux années 1990

L'enseignement du français est apparu dans les programmes d'éducation au Chili à partir de la fin du XIXe siècle, porté par l'influence culturelle et littéraire de la France sur la scène mondiale à l'époque. La création de l'Institut Pédagogique – aujourd'hui l'Université Métropolitaine des Sciences de l'Éducation – en 1889, et la présence de linguistes pionniers comme Rodolfo Lenz, qui ont modernisé le système d'enseignement de langues étrangères au pays, ont permis de consolider l'intégration du français dans les cursus scolaires.

Le positionnement du français comme seconde langue d'enseignement au Chili s'est poursuivi durant la première moitié du XXe siècle, pour ensuite être progressivement ralenti par la montée de l'anglais. Puis, en 1980, la réforme de l'éducation a donné un nouvel élan à la place du français, en instaurant

l'obligation d'enseigner deux langues étrangères dans les dernières années du cours primaire, bien que les moyens mis à disposition des enseignants pour offrir un apprentissage de qualité étaient souvent insuffisants.

Mais avec l'internationalisation croissante de l'économie, la mondialisation de la culture et l'hégémonie américaine dans la sphère technologique, l'anglais a peu à peu supplanté le français comme langue étrangère de référence et d'enseignement.

Étant donné ce contexte mondial, les réformes successives du système d'éducation de la fin des années 1990 ont orienté les politiques linguistiques vers un objectif clair : proposer l'anglais comme unique langue seconde d'enseignement obligatoire. Le programme "Inglés Abre Puertas", lancé en 2003 par le ministère de l'Éducation du Chili, incarne cette volonté de faire de l'anglais la langue seconde dominante.

Conséquence directe : le français a progressivement disparu des programmes d'enseignement public chiliens entre 1998 et 2004, provoquant du même coup une diminution des opportunités de formation des professeurs et de la disponibilité de matériel de français langue seconde.

L'état actuel de l'enseignement du français au Chili

Selon les chiffres rapportés par l'Institut Français, le français comme langue étrangère est enseigné dans 125 établissements d'éducation et centres de langue au Chili, appuyés par un total de 250 professeurs qui enseignent à 12 000 élèves.

Toutefois, bien que les plus jeunes générations se soient tournées vers l'anglais comme langue d'internationalisation, ils continuent d'exister un intérêt pour l'apprentissage du français au Chili. Daniela Quinteros, professeure de français et coordonnatrice de mobilité à l'Université Bernardo O'Higgins, l'a noté dans ses expériences de travail : « Dans le centre de langues où j'ai travaillé à Santiago, le français était la deuxième langue la plus sollicitée, soit parce que les gens l'aimaient particulièrement, parce qu'ils l'avaient appris au lycée plus jeunes et voulaient le récupérer, ou qu'ils voulaient voyager. Par contre, il y avait peu d'endroits où le français était enseigné à prix accessible, particulièrement à l'extérieur de Santiago ». Dans ce contexte, il était difficile de répondre à ce désir d'apprendre le français qui n'est pas pris en charge par le système éducatif. L'apparition de l'internet a cependant ouvert de nouvelles portes d'accès à l'apprentissage. Daniela Quinteros l'a constaté : « Aujourd'hui les gens peuvent se connecter en ligne, j'ai eu des étudiants de l'extrême Sud du pays. Je sens que cette disponibilité a permis que l'enseignement du français ait pris son envol ».

Le rapprochement entre l'espagnol et d'autres langues latines comme l'italien, le portugais et le français, peut aussi jouer en faveur de ce dernier, en autant qu'il existe des opportunités de l'apprendre.

Le français, une porte ouverte vers des opportunités internationales / Une langue minoritaire dans un monde hispanophone, mais pas marginale

Alors pourquoi apprendre le français dans un pays hispanophone où l'anglais s'est imposé comme langue seconde et langue des affaires ? Parce que la connaissance d'une troisième langue continue d'ouvrir des portes – parfois là où on ne les attend pas, quant à des opportunités d'éducation et de travail.

Comme le mentionne Daniela Quinteros, «aujourd'hui l'anglais se tient pour acquis, mais le français permet de faire un pas de plus. Il apporte une valeur ajoutée. En parlant anglais et français, il est possible d'accéder à toute autre gamme d'opportunités de travail ».

En effet, dans le domaine du commerce international, plusieurs entreprises françaises sont présentes au Chili, notamment dans les secteurs de l'énergie, des infrastructures, de la distribution ou de la technologie. Sur le plan académique, les étudiants chiliens qui parlent français ont accès à un vaste réseau d'universités francophones, non seulement en France mais aussi en Belgique, en Suisse, au Canada ou en Afrique.

Il serait donc erroné de penser que le français est condamné à rester marginal dans un contexte hispanophone. Au contraire, il joue un rôle stratégique dans le développement du multilinguisme.

Tel que mentionné, de plus en plus, les employeurs valorisent les compétences en plusieurs langues, non seulement pour des raisons pratiques, mais aussi pour ce qu'elles révèlent du profil culturel et intellectuel d'un candidat.

Par ailleurs, la francophonie, qui réunit 321 millions de locuteurs distribués sur les 5 continents, est aussi entendue comme espace culturel et géopolitique qui joue un rôle croissant dans les relations internationales. Des projets éducatifs et culturels unissent aujourd'hui le Chili et le monde francophone, à travers des échanges universitaires, des activités culturelles comme le Festival de la Francophonie, qui se déroule chaque année, ou encore des jumelages entre villes.

Conclusion : une langue d'avenir pour ceux qui osent la différence

L'histoire de l'enseignement du français au Chili reflète certainement la façon dont les systèmes d'éducation s'adaptent aux priorités culturelles et linguistiques dominantes de leur époque. Malgré tout, même si le français n'est plus la langue seconde par défaut qu'elle était il y a trente ans, elle n'a rien perdu de sa valeur. Au Chili, elle rejoint une communauté de 20 000 apprenants et est désormais une langue choisie, souvent par intérêt, parfois pour s'en rapprocher à nouveau, mais toujours avec une certaine conscience de sa richesse et des opportunités qu'elle peut ouvrir, étant la 5e langue la plus parlée au monde.

Dans un monde où la communication est reine, où les frontières culturelles s'estompent et où la différence devient un atout, parler français dans un pays hispanophone devient un marqueur culturel distinctif et aussi une façon d'affirmer une ouverture sur le monde.

¹Memoria chilena. "Rodolfo Lenz (1863-1938)"

²<https://www.memoriachilena.gob.cl/602/w3-article-3691.html>

³Antoine, Marie-Noëlle. 2007. "El francés en el sistema educativo chileno: causa perdida o Caballo de Troya para un cambio". Revista Contextos, UMCE, N-18.

⁴Institut Français. « Le français au Chili ». <https://www.institutofrances.cl/fr/cooperation/le-francais-au-chili/?utm-source=chatgpt.com/>

⁵Institut Français. « Le français au Chili ». <https://www.institutofrances.cl/fr/cooperation/le-francais-au-chili/?utm-source=chatgpt.com/>

⁶Organisation internationale de la Francophonie. « La Francophonie en bref ». <https://www.francophonie.org/la-francophonie-en-bref-754>

O canto internacional

Ensinar português no Chile: entre palavras, sotaques e pontes culturais

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Certa vez, Paulo Freire disse: “Educação não transforma o mundo. Educação muda as pessoas. Pessoas transformam o mundo”, e nisso acredito. Nesta oportunidade aproveito para unir duas paixões: a de escrever — considerando que sou jornalista de formação e amo esta proximidade com o universo das palavras — e a de falar sobre o impacto da Educação na vida de jovens estudantes, especialmente no ensino da minha língua, o português.

Quando falamos sobre o ensino do português para estudantes hispanofalantes, em específico os sul-americanos, sempre busco aproximá-los da realidade do Chile e assim destacar a relevância de aprender este novo idioma. Dados do Serviço Nacional de Turismo (Sernatur) indicam que, somente em 2024, 787.036 brasileiros visitaram o Chile, número que fica atrás apenas dos hermanos argentinos no ranking de visitantes estrangeiros. Creio que a proximidade geográfica, a curiosidade por conhecer a neve e o fator financeiro desempenham um papel importante na hora do brasileiro decidir qual lugar visitar. Não é só o setor do Turismo que se beneficia, outros setores também ganham.

Mas voltando ao que falei antes, mais do que aprender um novo idioma, com suas competências gramaticais e diferenciais fonéticos, o que por si só termina em boas risadas entre todos, ensinar português é, para mim, uma experiência tão desafiadora quanto fascinante. Entre semelhanças enganosas e diferenças profundas, a sala de aula se torna um espaço de constante descoberta mútua. É como ter um emprego que é certo para mim, como dizemos no Brasil, e poder proporcionar ainda mais acesso à cultura e à educação. Afinal, como disse antes, acredito na ideia de Paulo Freire de que “pessoas transformam o mundo”.

Já em sala de aula, a história vai além: os estudantes estão sempre com o lápis em mãos preparados para registrar cada expressão nova que escutam e escutam muito bem. Posso afirmar isso com total certeza, após ver dezenas de pessoas repetindo o que digo e a maneira como digo. Se você também é educador, deixo aqui um pedido com carinho: reforce sempre a seus estudantes que está tudo bem errar durante o aprendizado e que estão juntos nesta viagem. Além disso, que não há problema em ter sotaque, porque muitos se sentem envergonhados por temerem ser considerados “gringos” ou pensam que precisam falar igual a um nativo. Ressalte que o sotaque é parte de quem é, de sua identidade, de suas raízes e isso não deve ser abandonado.

E já que falamos sobre o “como”, creio ser de total importância pensar na maneira como realizamos esse repasse de conhecimentos. Para mim, uma abordagem comunicativa é uma das peças fundamentais neste processo, junto da necessidade

de adaptação na hora de ensinar. Reflitamos juntos: não dá para fazer o mesmo para todos, uma vez que temos realidades distintas e pessoas com necessidades específicas. Para uma aula mais efetiva, sempre busco demonstrar o quanto estamos próximos (Brasil, Chile e demais países da América do Sul) e ao mesmo tempo com diferenças tão acentuadas, seja por razões culturais, gramaticais, de vocabulário, etc.

De toda forma, mesmo estando próximos, é preciso entender quais são os desafios que um docente pode ter na hora de ensinar português. É comum se deparar em sala de aula com estudantes que subestimam a dificuldade do português porque parece fácil e a questão aqui é como demonstramos que esse pensamento é limitado e pode levar a erros comuns, afinal, por exemplo, embaraçada não é o mesmo que embaraçada, do espanhol, o que pode gerar situações embaraçosas.

Outro grande desafio é a fossilização de erros, que é quando um estudante insiste, não necessariamente de modo intencional, em erros no processo de aquisição de um novo idioma. Aqui falamos, por exemplo, do portunhol, algo que pode se acentuar com o tempo, o que pode ser trabalhado com iniciativas como: momentos de prática fonética e aprendizado de vocabulário, com a devida correção por parte do docente, mas sem desmotivar o aluno. Para lidar com a mescla de idiomas, uma forma assertiva é fazer uma comparação direta com o espanhol. Finalmente, é mais fácil aprender um idioma de maneira imersa e assim trabalhar a fossilização, e alguns recursos podem ajudar tais como: áudios, leituras, entre outros.

Por fim, sobre os principais ganhos em toda minha jornada como educador: é gratificante quando um estudante te olha e diz: “profe, sabe que eu finalmente consegui entender uma música ou vi um filme que tanto gostava, em português?” ou “eu conheci um brasileiro no Costanera Center e nós tivemos uma conversa super interessante (em meu idioma)”. Junto a isso, sinto que estou construindo uma espécie de ponte cultural entre Brasil, Chile e demais países latinoamericanos abrindo portas que vão além do turismo, como a possibilidade de seguir estudando, formando profissionais mais competentes e até impulsionando a criação e expansão de negócios, o que contribui para o desenvolvimento do país.

Em linhas gerais, considero que não importa o que aconteça, ensinar português em um país de língua espanhola é mais do que compartilhar regras gramaticais e abrir portas. Cada sala de aula é um lugar onde todos aprendem, observam coisas diferentes e, por fim, compartilham saberes e levam consigo aprendizados para a vida.

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